

Swedigarch Module 4 SEAD Database Data Management Plan

Swedigarch

Swedish National Infrastructure for Digital Archaeology

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Project abstract

Module 4 of the Swedish National Infrastructure for Digital Archaeology (Swedigarch) focuses on Archaeological Science Research Data, of which the primary tool for gathering and disseminating this data is the Strategic Environmental Archaeology Database (SEAD).

Therefore, this Data Management Plan echoes that of the entire Swedigarch infrastructure, but focuses specifically on the management plan for the data that makes up SEAD.

SEAD is a national research infrastructure for environmental archaeology data developed and managed at the Environmental Archaeology Lab (MAL) in collaboration with Humlab at Umeå University, Sweden. SEAD is part of an international network of research infrastructures for environmental archaeology and Quaternary paleoecology, enabling collaboration and data sharing among researchers worldwide. Its mission is to provide online tools to support research in environmental archaeology and to promote online access of relevant datasets. The system grants the online storage, extraction, analysis, and visualization of data on past climates, environments, and human impacts

SEAD is a relational database, where data are stored in a complex but user-friendly web of database tables that allows for efficient data retrieval and querying. The SEAD database structure is adapted to follow standard archaeological workflow processes, with a specific focus on environmental archaeology. Datasets stored in SEAD are structured hierarchically, with the site at the top level, and the samples (and results from analyses) at the lower level. The initial geographical scope of SEAD focused primarily on Sweden and Scandinavia, but coverage continuously improves now to include other European datasets, as well as beyond. There are currently 1655 sites in SEAD, with 15,000 linked datasets.

SEAD provides online access to raw data and basic analytical tools to assist interpretation. Datasets in SEAD are primarily biological and chemical/physical proxy data, i.e., fossil frequencies and measured variables derived from soil samples taken from archaeological and natural deposits. The database also includes geoarchaeological data from the analysis of ceramic thin sections and dendrochronological results. Dates, such as radiocarbon or calendar dates, are linked to samples where available, as are bibliographic information and extensive metadata. These allow for a large degree of linking with other databases. Further datasets, although few, include the results from modern biological sampling (insects, pollen, plants). Modern ecological reference data are included for most insect species, allowing for extensive and detailed paleoenvironmental reconstructions.

Several mechanisms ensure that only reliable data are available through SEAD. All submitted data are subject to evaluation in a peer review process where any inconsistencies or problems with the data are corrected in communication with the data provider. This model is integral to the project structure and essential for ensuring transparency in scientific research. The database also includes opportunities to indicate data quality, authorship, origin, method descriptions, and other hard-wired quality indicators and tracers.

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Funding information

Is there any additional information concerning the funding that you would like to add (Ref.UmUB.01)?

- YES

Funder(s). Please chose the applicable funder from the list. Multiple choices possible. If Other, please specify in the Additional Information text field. Additional funding information can also be added in the Additional Information text field (Ref.UmUB.02).

- VR Swedish Research Council (Vetenskapsrådet)

Will there be any extra costs related to data management? If yes, please answer this question with an estimate of the extra costs (TC) and/or additional working hours for data management in the project that are NOT already covered by grant funding in the comment are. (Ref.UmUB.03)

- The data management costs are an inbuilt part of SEAD's budget and staffing plan.

0: GDPR compliance

We have read and understood the above declaration and hereby certify that this DMP contains only information about project members such as Principal Investigator (PI) and/or contact person(s) (Ref.UmUB.0/01).

- YES

I. Responsibility and resources

Please provide information about everyone involved in managing the data for this project. Describe who is responsible for what. It is especially important to indicate who is responsible for datasets that are produced/handled at different institutions. This information is essential data archiving. The research principal (institution) is responsible for archiving the data.

Name	email address	ORCID number	Roll
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Johan von Boer	johan.von.boer@umu.se		Database Developer

Affiliation (Department/Institution/Unit) of all contributors. Please select the correct main department/ institution affiliation for all project contributors named in the above question from the drop-down menu or else choose "Others" and specify in the comment area (multiple options possible).(Ref.UmUB.1/02)

- Department of Historical, Philosophical and Religious Studies
- Humlab

Who is responsible for data management during the project? (Multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.1/03)

- Project leader
- Principal Investigator (PI)
- See list above

What resources will be required for data management? (Multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.1/04)

- Extra costs (money and/or staff)
- Repository accounts
- Special software
- Internal secure storage
- Note that SEAD is a relational database.

II: Data description - reuse of existing data and/or production of new data

Will the data used in this project consist of newly-generated data, pre-existing data or both? The number of questions in this section is varying - depending on your answer. Only if your answer is "Both newly-generated and pre-existing data" will all the questions be visible. If your answer is either "Previously-existing" or "Newly-generated", only the answering options connected to the respective data will be available for answering. (Ref.UmUB.2/01)

- Previously-existing data

Please describe the dataset(s) in the project! The description may represent a more abstract concept, which does not have to point to individual files. (Ref.UmUB.2/02)

- SEAD contains a variety of datasets from numerous data providers. SEAD is a relational database, where data are stored in a complex but user-friendly web of database tables that allows for efficient data retrieval and querying. The SEAD database structure is adapted to follow standard archaeological workflow processes, with a specific focus on environmental archaeology. Datasets stored in SEAD are structured hierarchically, with the site at the top level, and the samples (and results from analyses) at the lower level. The initial geographical scope of SEAD focused primarily on Sweden and Scandinavia, but coverage continuously improves now to include other European datasets, as well as beyond.

Data Quality Assurance measures (Sustainability of digital formats): Which of the following options will you apply to assure quality and integrity of collected, reused, or created data? (multiple choices possible) (Ref.UmUB.2/03)

- 6. Other measures: SEAD contains a variety of datasets from numerous data providers. The data ownership remains with the original providers. However, our database is fully tracked, with version control, so it is possible to go back to any given state of the database. (This is especially important for database users, who can give the specific version number used in their publications, which ensures reproducibility of their work, as others can go back to that version to extract data. This also permits researchers to compare the changes in the data over time.)
- We are in the process of implementing a system wherein the data provider can check the quality of the data after it has been ingested to our database. Perhaps a formal agreement with the data provider, which clearly spells out responsibilities for data quality control.

Format(s) of pre-existing datasets. Please give the file name(s) of your pre-existing data files incl. file extensions/suffixes, separated by commas. (Ref.UmUB.2/05)

- The full list of the data, and the changes to the data, is available at https://github.com/humlab-sead/sead_change_control this includes all data sets provided by all data providers.

Do the pre-existing datasets already have a definite distribution (e.g. persistent identifier, access point or location, title, ...)? (Ref.UmUB.2/06)

- Yes

Data access-point(s): please list URL(s) used to access to the pre-existing dataset(s) or resource(s) (e.g. DOIs, simple URLs,... separat by commas). (Ref.UmUB.2/7)

- <https://browser.sead.se/>

Data access: please indicate the access conditions for your pre-existing dataset. (Ref.UmUB.2/8)

- Open

License(s) of re-used data. Please select the licens that applies to your pre-existing data set(s). If Other, please give a file locator (e.g. URL) of the given licens. (Multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.2/9)

- CC-BY-4.0

III: Data documentation and data quality

Are you planning to use controlled vocabularies and metadata standards to describe your research data?

- Yes, SEAD has a clearly defined data structure to which new datasets are mapped. The public-facing summary of this structure is located at <https://humlab-sead.github.io/sead-schema/>

Which metadata standard do you plan to use when describing your data (newly created or/and pre-existing data)? (Multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.3/02).

- 8. ARIADNE infrastructure
- 10. Own controlled vocabulary, SEAD uses a defined taxonomy for insects and plants, and is the registered authority for this vocabulary. SEAD is a multidisciplinary database, using a variety of vocabularies from many sources.

Please indicate which repository you are planning to choose to describe your data (either by choosing a repository from the list below

- GitHub
- Researchdata.se
- Zenodo, thus far we have not made use of the Swedigarch Zenodo community, but it is very possible we will do so.

Documentation of data quality and protection measures. What methods to ensure the quality of your data and the integrity of your data files do you plan to use? Several answers are possible (Ref.UmUB.3/04).

- Registered reports
- Validation of data input
- Supplementary documentation (e.g. codebook/ variable description, ELN, questionnaire, stimuli)
- Integrity check of data-files
- Data clean(s)ing
- The Data providers are responsible for ensuring their data is properly in order when they submit it.

IV: Storage and backup during the project

Where are you planning to store and backup your research data during the project? (Multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.4/01)

- The SEAD database is hosted on our own in-house servers.

How big is the data volume that you will need to store and backup during the project? (Ref.UmUB.4/02)

- < 1 GB, the data are stored in text as a relational database.

Which kind of security measures are you going to employ to protect your data during the project? (multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.4/03)

- Multi-factor authentication
- Password protection
- While the data itself is freely available to access, the database is protected against unauthorized modifications by IP restrictions.

V: Legal and ethical aspects

Will the creation, collection or reuse of the dataset(s) in your project entail any of the following: (Ref.UmUB.5/01)

- NONE of the above listed, the data in SEAD is archaeological in nature, and does not contain personal data.

Which measures will you take to prevent illegitimate access to personal data or other sensitive data in your dataset(s)? (multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.5/02)

- NONE of the above listed, the data in SEAD is archaeological in nature, and does not contain personal data.

Will the creation, collection or reuse of dataset(s) in your project include any of the following: (Ref.UmUB.3/03)

- NONE of the above listed, the data in SEAD is archaeological in nature, and does not contain sensitive data.

Has an ethical review been performed for your project? (Ref.UmUB.5/04)

- No, the data in SEAD is archaeological in nature, and does not contain personal data or require an ethical review.

License. If your data can be open available, which license are you planning to provide for each of the newly created datasets? PLEASE NOTE that information about licenses for your pre-existing datasets has been given in Section I/ Q13. If you choose 12. OTHER please specify which license you choose in the comment area. You are free to choose NO LICENSE (option 13) but please be aware that this choice makes your dataset less FAIR. (Multiple options are possible.) Data that cannot be open do not receive a licence. (Ref.UmUB.5/05)

- CC BY-4.0

VI: Data sharing and long-term preservation

Data location and distribution. Where are you planning to make your dataset(s), documentation and/or metadata accessible? (Multiple options possible for different datasets/files) (Ref.UmUB.6/01)

- Researchdata.se
- OTHER (please specify): The plan is for SEAD to be a long-term research infrastructure resource as part of Swedigarch.

Accessibility of data - content. What kind of data, metadata or documentation material will be made available? (Multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.6/02)

- Metadata AND datafiles

Accessibility of data - timeframe. When will your data files and/or metadata and documentation be accessible? (Multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.6/3)

- Continuously (as produced and updated)

Archiving. Please NOTE that long-term archiving of public records (allmänna handlingar) is mandatory. However, Umeå University does NOT automatically provide storage space for archiving of research data.

- Ideally, this project will remain funded long-term and the database will always be accessible. Should this prove not to be the case, steps will be made to archive/preserve the data.

Software required for the use of the archived research data. Will there be a special software, source code or other types of services be necessary in order to understand, re-use, analyse, or interact with your data? If the answer is yes, please cite the software used to produce your data in the comment area. (Ref.UmUB.6/05)

- No, there is a freely available web interface to access SEAD data.

Accessibility of your dataset for re-use due to special software. Will the software you use to collect, handle, transform, refine or analyse your data also be needed to replicate and rerun experiments and will it be a part of your datasets or open datafiles? If the answer is yes, please cite the software used to produce your data in the comment area (references including version number and URLs) or explain how it can be otherwise accessed (e.g. if the software/code is created within the project). (Ref.UmUB.6/06)

- No

Will the software/ code you are going to use to collect, create, handle, transform, refine or analyse data be ... (please chose an answer; multiple options possible) (Ref.UmUB.6/07)

- Proprietary/ Commercial (e.g. Matlab, Stata)
- Non-proprietary/ Open Source (e.g. Python, R, XSLT)
- The SEAD web browser provides some data manipulation and transformation prior to export, but most users will choose their preferred methods after export.

Cloud software, SaaS: Are you planning to use software that is based in a "cloud"/ Software-as-a-service (SaaS) to create, handle, transform, refine or analys data in the project? If you chose YES please specify in the comment area. (Ref.UmUB.6/08)

- NO

VII: Funding requirements fulfilled for initial version

I hereby certify that I submitted the initial version of the DMP for archiving purposes. OBS! Please note that dmp-online does not automatically send the dmp for archiving (it has to actively downloaded and/or printed and handed in at your respective institute administration in charge of document handling). If you need help with finding out who is in charge of document handling at your institution please contact the library (Ref.UmUB.7/01)

- Yes